

**11th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
“FUNDAMENTAL AND APPLIED PROBLEMS OF MODERN PHYSICS”
Dedicated to 110th Anniversary of Academician S.A. Azimov**

**11-я МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ
«ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ФИЗИКИ»
Посвящённая 110-летию академика С.А. Азимова**

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ТРУДЫ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ

110

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UZBEKISTAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES
S.A. AZIMOV PHYSICAL-TECHNICAL INSTITUTE
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**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ
И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ
СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ФИЗИКИ**

**FUNDAMENTAL AND APPLIED
PROBLEMS OF MODERN PHYSICS**

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МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ**

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OF INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE**

16 - 18 октября

Ташкент 2025 г.

**АКАДЕМИЯ НАУК РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН
ФИЗИКО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЙ ИНСТИТУТ ИМЕНИ С.А. АЗИМОВА
СОВЕТ ФИЗИКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА
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ВВЕДЕНИЕ

Физико-технический институт (ФТИ), основанный в 1943 году, является одним из старейших научных учреждений Академии наук Узбекистана. За годы своей деятельности институт сыграл важную роль в формировании многих научных направлений, которые впоследствии стали основными областями исследований в Академии наук Узбекистана. Среди них физическая электроника, физика твёрдого тела, физика полупроводников, ядерная физика, физика высоких энергий и космических лучей, технологии солнечной энергетики и материаловедение высоких температур. На базе научных направлений и подразделений ФТИ были созданы Институт ядерной физики (1956 г.), Институт электроники (1967 г.), и в 1987 г. - НПО "Физика-Солнце" АН РУз. Институт материаловедения организован в 1993 г. на базе ряда лабораторий ФТИ и его Опытного производства с Большой Солнечной Печью (БСП).

Признанием заслуг ученых НПО "Физика-Солнце" АН РУз явилось издание Указа Президента РУз №УП-4512 от 01.03.2013 г. «О мерах по дальнейшему развитию альтернативных источников энергии» и Постановления Президента РУз №ПП-1929 от 01.03.2013г. «О создании Международного института солнечной энергии». За крупный вклад в науку в области физики полупроводников в 2007 г. сотрудники Института академик М.С.Саидов, доктора ф.-м.н. И.Г. Атабаев и А.С. Саидов удостоены Государственной премии Республики Узбекистан в области науки и техники. За разработку и создание современных систем прямого преобразования солнечного излучения в электрическую энергию на основе кремниевых фотопреобразователей, коллектив ученых Института - С. Дадамухамедов, Х. Сабилов, М.Н. Турсунов, И.А. Юлдашев во главе с академиком Р.А. Муминовым удостоен в 2013 г. Государственной премии Республики Узбекистан в области науки и техники.

В Институте длительное время работали и работают в настоящее время видные ученые-физики: академик С.А. Азимов - основатель научной школы физики высоких и сверхвысоких энергий, высокотемпературного гелиоматериаловедения в нашей стране; академик У.А. Арифов – создатель школы физической электроники в Узбекистане; академики С.У. Умаров, Э.И. Адирович, М.С. Саидов и Р.А. Муминов – основатели различных направлений физики полупроводников, академик С.В. Стародубцев – создатель научной школы физики твёрдого тела и один из организаторов Института ядерной физики, член – корр. АН РУз Г.Я. Умаров – основатель научной школы гелиотехнических исследований в нашей Республике, академик Т.Т. Рискиев, создавший совместно с академиком С.А. Азимовым школу высокотемпературного материаловедения, академики К.Г. Гуламов, Б.С. Юлдашев и Т.С. Юлдашбаев, которые развили научную школу физики высоких энергий и космических лучей, основанную академиком С.А. Азимовым.

С 1965 г. ФТИ АН РУз издаёт Международный журнал «Гелиотехника». Журнал переводится на английский язык американской компанией «Аллертон Пресс», издаётся в США под названием «Applied Solar Energy» и распространяется по подписке. Журнал «Applied Solar Energy» индексируется в научной базе «SCOPUS» престижных международных журналов.

В этом 2025 году в Физико-техническом институте имени С.А.Азимова Академии наук Республики Узбекистан уже в одиннадцатый раз проводится ставшая традиционной Международная конференция «Фундаментальные и прикладные проблемы современной физики». В этот раз мероприятие посвящено 110-летию со дня рождения выдающегося учёного, академика Садыка Азимова.

Для участия в конференции принимались научные работы, выполненные в последние годы по следующим направлениям:

1. физика ядра и элементарных частиц (включая прикладные аспекты, физику высоких энергий и космических лучей); 2. физика полупроводников и твёрдого тела (в том числе физика плазмы и её приложения); 3. возобновляемые источники энергии и их использование (включая гелиоматериаловедение).

Приятно отметить, что по тематике конференции было подано 185 научных работ, среди которых 74 от зарубежных учёных из США, Японии, России, Пакистана, Казахстана, Азербайджана, Турции, Беларуси, Таджикистана и других стран.

Мы убеждены, что данная конференция станет эффективной площадкой для обмена новейшими научными достижениями между исследователями из разных стран, а также будет способствовать развитию новых научных связей и формированию перспективных международных коллабораций.

Председатель оргкомитета – проф., д.ф.-м.н. Хусниддин Олимов

INTRODUCTION

Founded in 1943, the Physical-Technical Institute (PhTI) is one of the oldest research institutions of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences. Over the years, it has played a key role in shaping many scientific disciplines that later became the core research areas of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences (UZAS). These include physical electronics, solid-state physics, semiconductor physics, nuclear physics, high-energy and cosmic ray physics, solar energy technologies, and high-temperature materials science.

On the basis of scientific areas and divisions of PhTI, several institutions were created, such as the Institute of Nuclear Physics (1956), Institute of Electronics (1967) and SPA “Physics-Sun” of the UzAS (1987). The Institute of Materials Science, based on a number of laboratories of PhTI and its pilot production facility with a Big Solar Furnace (BSF), was established in 1993.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures for further development of alternative energy sources” №UP-4512 on 01.03.2013 and the corresponding Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the establishment of the International Institute of solar energy” №PP-1929 on 01.03.2013 are recognition of achievements of scientists from PhTI of SPA “Physics-Sun” of the UzAS. For important contribution to science in the field of semiconductor physics, the Institute scientists - Academician M.S. Saidov, Dr. Sci. A.S. Saidov and Dr. Sci. I.G. Atabaev, were awarded the State Prize of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of science and technology in 2007. The team of scientists of the Institute - S. Dadamuhamedov, H. Sabirov, M.N. Tursunov, and I.A. Yuldashev, headed by Academician R.A. Muminov, was awarded in 2013 the State Prize of Uzbekistan in the field of science and technology for the development and creation of modern systems of direct conversion of solar radiation into electrical energy, based on silicon solar cells.

Many prominent physicists have worked in the past and are presently working at the institute. They founded the different well-known scientific schools and research directions in Uzbekistan: academician S.A. Azimov - founder of the scientific school of high-energy and ultra-high-energy physics and high-temperature materials science; academician U.A. Arifov - creator of the School of Physical Electronics; academicians S.U. Umarov, E.I. Adirovich, M.S. Saidov and R.A. Muminov - founders of various research areas in Semiconductor Physics; academician S.V. Starodubtsev – founder of scientific school of solid state physics and one of the founders of the Institute of Nuclear Physics; correspondent-member of UzAS G.Ya.Umarov – founder of the scientific school in applied solar energy research; academician T.T. Riskiev, who created, together with academician S.A. Azimov, the school of high temperature materials science; academicians K.G. Gulamov, B.S. Yuldashev, and T.S. Yuldashbaev, who developed further the scientific school of high energy and cosmic ray physics, founded by academician S.A. Azimov.

Since 1965, PhTI publishes the international journal “Applied Solar Energy”. The journal is translated into English by the American company “Allerton Press” and is published in the United States and distributed by subscription. The journal “Applied Solar Energy” is indexed in the “SCOPUS” scientific database of the prestigious international journals.

In 2025, the Physical-Technical Institute named after S.A. Azimov of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan is hosting, for the eleventh time, the traditional International Conference on “Fundamental and Applied Problems of Modern Physics.” This year, the event is dedicated to the 110th anniversary of the birth of the outstanding scientist, Academician Sadyk Azimov.

Scientific papers completed in recent years were accepted for participation in the following fields:

1. Nuclear and elementary particle physics (including applied aspects, high-energy physics, and cosmic rays);
2. Semiconductor and solid-state physics (including plasma physics and its applications);
3. Renewable energy sources and their applications (including heliomaterials science).

It is gratifying to note that 185 scientific papers were submitted to the conference, including 74 from foreign researchers representing the USA, Japan, Russia, Pakistan, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Belarus, Tajikistan, and other countries.

We are confident that this conference will serve as an effective platform for the exchange of the latest scientific achievements among researchers from different countries and will contribute to the development of new scientific collaborations and the establishment of promising international partnerships.

Chair of the organizing committee – Prof. Dr. Khusniddin Olimov

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ

СЕКЦИЯ I. ФИЗИКА ЯДРА И ЭЛЕМЕНТАРНЫХ ЧАСТИЦ

МЕТОД ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СВЕТИМОСТИ РЕАКЦИЙ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ДЕЛЬТА-ЭЛЕКТРОНОВ ИЗ ВНУТРЕННЕЙ МИШЕНИ НУКЛОТРОНА	
Игамкулов З.А., Дряблов Д.К.	19
OBSERVATION OF ALIGNMENT IN THE AZIMUTH-PSEUDORAPIDITY MATRIX IN CENTRAL COLLISIONS OF ^{32}S NUCLEI WITH HEAVY NUCLEI OF EMULSION AT $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 20$ GEV	
Vladimir V. Lugovoi and Kadir G. Gulamov	25
ANALYSIS OF TRANSVERSE MOMENTUM SPECTRA OF CHARGED HADRONS IN PROTON-PROTON COLLISIONS AT $\sqrt{s} = 7$ and 13 TeV USING THE TSALLIS DISTRIBUTION	
Khusnidin Olimov, Kobil Musaev, Maratbek Shodmonov.	31
DEPENDENCE OF THE ALTERNATING-PARITY SPECTRA OF THE RIGID ASYMMETRIC ROTATOR ON THE ANGULAR VARIABLE OF THE POLAR COORDINATE	
Nadirbekov M. S., Kudiratorov S. N., Kungurov F. R.	32
ВЛИЯНИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ПЕРВЫХ ЯДРО-ЯДЕРНЫХ ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЙ НА РАЗВИТИЕ КАСКАДНЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ В ШИРОКИХ АТМОСФЕРНЫХ ЛИВНЯХ	
Федосимова Анастасия	37
DAVYDOV-CHABAN MODEL WITH DAVIDSON POTENTIAL	
M.S. Nadirbekov, Zebo Sobirova and K.K. Shadmanov	38
THREE-MAGNON SYSTEMS IN THE HEISENBERG MODEL	
Sadulla Tashpulatov	44
DOSIMETRY ANALYSIS OF CS-131 LOADED BIOPOLYMER GRANULES IN RADIONUCLIDE AND X-RAY BASED HYBRID THERAPY OF BREAST CANCER CELLS WITH MONTE CARLO SIMULATIONS	
Ahmet Ünlü, İsmail Boztosun, Orkun Hasekioğlu	50
LOW COST NANOAMPEREMETER BASED ON SWITCHED INTEGRATOR CIRCUIT	
Alisher Temirzhanov, Timur Zholdybayev, Bakhtiyar Sadykov, Gulnaz Ussabayeva, Bek Duisebayev, Kayrat Mendibayev.	51
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ФАЗОВОГО ПЕРЕХОДА ОТ АДРОННОЙ МАТЕРИИ К КВАРК-ГЛЮОННОЙ ПЛАЗМЕ В p+Pb, Xe+Xe И Pb+Pb СТОЛКНОВЕНИЯХ НА БОЛЬШОМ АДРОННОМ КОЛЛАЙДЕРЕ	
Х.К. Олимов, А.Н. Кахорова	52
APPLICATION OF THE CORRELATION CURVE METHOD TO INCREASE THE ACCURACY OF DETERMINING THE ENERGY OF COSMIC RAYS ABOVE 1 TeV	
Sayora Ibraimova	54
KVARK-GLYUON PLAZMASIDAN KINETIK MUZLASHGACHA: Pb+Pb TO'QNASHUVLAR TIZIMI TAHLILI	
Olimov Xusniddin Kosimovich, Tohirov Azizjon Muzaffar o'g'li, Xudoyberdiyeva Shohida Aliyevna, Kaخورova Aziza Nuridinovna	55
PHOTONEUTRON AND NEUTRON REACTIONS IN NUCLEAR ASTROPHYSICS.	
Satimboy Palvanov, Saidmuhammad Ahmedov, Asror Ramazanov.	57
CALCULATION OF THE CHEMICAL FREEZE-OUT PARAMETERS IN Pb-Pb AND Xe-Xe COLLISIONS AT THE LHC	
Khusnidin Olimov, Maratbek Shodmonov, Kobil Musaev, Satimboy Polvonov.	59

ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ УГЛА НАКЛОНА ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ВЫРАБОТКИ СОЛНЕЧНОЙ ЭНЕРГИИ В ПАРКЕНТЕ	
Ш.Ш.Шосайтов, М.У. Носиров, Ж.З. Ахадов	327
СЕКЦИЯ III. ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫЕ ИСТОЧНИКИ ЭНЕРГИИ, МАТЕРИАЛОВЕДЕНИЕ И ИХ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ	329
STABILITY OF NANO-CORONAELECTRETS BASED ON HDPE	
Aysel Nabiyeva Mammadli	330
DEGRADATION OF SOLAR CELLS BY IONIZING RADIATION BASED ON SILICON DOUBLE BARRIERS NANOSTRUCTURES	
Fakhraddin Pasha Abasov	332
EFFECT OF GAMMA RAYS ON THE ELECTRICAL AND PHOTOELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF GASE SINGLE CRYSTAL BEFORE INTERCALATION	
R.S. Madatov, L.E. Sadigli, R.M. Mamishova, A.Sh. Khaligzada	334
GAMMA IRRADIATION INDUCED STRUCTURAL MODIFICATIONS OF HDPE/GaAs COMPOSITE FILMS	
Nushaba Gadzhieva, Gunay Akhmedova	335
AGE DETERMINATION OF THE SAMPLE TAKEN FROM GOBUSTAN IN AZERBAIJAN	
Aybaniz Ahadova	339
EFFECT OF GAMMA IRADIATION ON THE ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF BILAYER STRUCTURES BASED ON POLYMER/CDS AND POLYMER/CUS NANOCOMPOSITES	
A.I. Gasimova, M.A. Nuriyev, A.A. Shukurova	341
OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF GAMMA IRRADIATION-MODIFIED PVA/CdS AND PVA/CuS NANOCOMPOSITES	
A.I. Gasimova, M.A. Nuriyev, A.A. Shukurova, I.M.Nuruyev	343
EFFECT OF NANOFILLERS Al_2O_3 AND SiO_2 ON DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF HIGH DENSITY POLYETHYLENE	
Rafiga İsmayilova, Aysel Nabiyeva Mammadli and Musafir Guliyev	345
ANALYSIS OF TRAP PARAMETERS USING THE COMPUTERIZED GLOW CURVE DECONVOLUTION (CGCD) METHOD	
Ahmad Ahadov, Sahib Mammadov, Aybaniz Ahadova, Akshin Abishov	347
DETERMINATION OF HIGH-TEMPERATURE CORROSION PARAMETERS OF ZIRCONIUM BERYLLIDES	
Timur Kulsartov, Inesh Kenzhina, Zhanna Zaurbekova, Yuriy Ponkratov, Yuriy Gordiyenko	349
SYNTHESIS OF α - Fe_2O_3 NANOPARTICLES BY CHEMICAL PRECIPITATION	
Odiljon Abdurakhmonov, Mastura Aripova, Sherzod Abdurakhmonov and Utkirjon Sharopov	350
PHASE ANALYSIS OF HEXAGONAL BORON NITRIDE NANOPARTICLES OBTAINED BY TWO-STEP THERMAL STRUCTURE	
Sh. Abdurakhmonov, M. Aripova, O. Abdurakhmonov and U. Sharopov	352
ANALYSIS OF THE STAGES OF SYNTHESIS OF HEXAGONAL BORON NITRIDE BY IR SPECTROSCOPY	
Sherzod Abdurakhmonov, Mastura Aripova, Odiljon Abdurakhmonov and Utkirjon Sharopov	353
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF H-BN NANOPARTICLES USING TEM AND HR-TEM METHODS	
	355

ANALYSIS OF TRAP PARAMETERS USING THE COMPUTERIZED GLOW CURVE DECONVOLUTION (CGCD) METHOD

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Abstract.

This study examines how thermal cleaning and irradiation doses affect the accuracy of quartz activation energy determination via the initial rise method. Isothermal decay of quartz deviates from both first- and second-order kinetics due to complex nature of the TL glow curve. Critically, the study refutes the longstanding assumption that initial rise methods are independent of kinetic order.

The quartz samples employed in this experiment were obtained from beach sand through conventional chemical separation methods. Subsequently, samples underwent hydrochloric acid (HCl) treatment, separation through heavy liquids, and etching in a 40% hydrofluoric acid (HF) solution. The precipitated fluorides were dissolved using HCl. Two primary experimental techniques are employed in thermoluminescence (TL) research to examine isothermal decay. The first, known as the residual isothermal decay method, involves annealing the irradiated sample in a

furnace post-irradiation, followed by cooling and measurement of the residual TL glow curve. The second approach, referred to as the prompt isothermal decay technique, measures TL directly while maintaining the sample at a stable temperature using a TL reader¹².

To determine activation energy, the study employed the initial rise (IR) method, which relies on the Arrhenius equation in the initial rise region—the low-temperature tail-of the glow curve, where recombination effects are negligible. The calculations were performed under both low- and high-dose conditions to evaluate the method's consistency across different trap-filling regimes.

The computerized deconvolution of complex glow curves into their individual components is applied using the TL Glow Curve Analyzer (TLanal) to evaluate the kinetic parameters using curve fitting methods. TLanal is written in C# using Visual Studio.NET and has been tested on Microsoft Windows-based operating systems. This program adopted a method based on the general one-trap TL equation. This method was used to analyze the TL glow curve³ with the traditional first-order, second-order, and general order kinetics model.

Additionally, numerical simulations were conducted using the OTOR model, which assumes the presence of a single active electron trap and one recombination center. The simulations explored two critical variables: the initial electron concentration (n_0), which corresponds to the irradiation dose, and the number of data points selected from the initial rise region for activation energy calculations. These factors were analyzed to assess their influence on the accuracy and reliability of the IR method.

The deconvolution of complex thermoluminescence (TL) glow curves into individual components is critical for dosimetric applications and kinetic parameter evaluation. CGCD methods, such as the TL Glow Curve Analyzer (TLanal), are widely employed to resolve overlapping peaks and assign kinetic orders (first-, second-, or general-order)⁴⁵⁶. TLanal, developed in C# for Windows-based systems, leverages a generalized one-trap TL equation to model glow curves and interpolate parameters (activation energy (E), frequency factor (s), and kinetic order (b)). Its accuracy is validated via the figure of merit ($FOM \leq 2.35\%$ in this study), ensuring reliable decomposition. The TL glow curve of natural quartz (2.19 kGy gamma dose) was decomposed into three peaks at ~145 °C, 175 °C, and 229 °C, consistent with thermal cleaning data.

CGCD analysis yielded general-order kinetics $b=1.10, 1.50, 1.10$ for the peaks 1, 2 and 3 respectively with $E=1.0$ eV, 1.15 eV, and 1.25 eV, aligning with literature (e.g., 0.95–1.1 eV for analogous quartz traps). The synergy of CGCD with isothermal decay and thermal cleaning methods strengthens the robustness of kinetic parameter extraction. While CGCD accounts for kinetic complexity, IR and isothermal decay provide model-independent validation for simpler traps. Discrepancies in TL parameter values highlight the necessity of multi-method approaches, particularly for mixed-order systems. These findings align with studies emphasizing the limitations of single-method analyses in natural quartz due to defect heterogeneity.

Key words: thermoluminescence, activation energy, initial rise method, thermal cleaning, CGCD method.

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